

A Proposed Ensemble Based Model to Classify the Personality Using Big-Five Model

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Abstract- Text is categorized using machine learning algorithms based on the sentiment polarity of the text. These machine learning-based approaches approach sentiment classification as a problem akin to document or subject classification. Nevertheless, this method has drawbacks including hard feature extraction, dimensionality expansion, and sparse feature vectors. In this article, we have combined machine learning and deep learning algorithms and proposed ensemble based framework to classify the personality. We have done different experiments with machine learning, deep learning and proposed model and found that our proposed model provided significant average accuracy about 67.452.

Index Terms- Personality Classification, OCEAN model, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Feature Extraction, Word Embedding.

I. INTRODUCTION

A person's unique manner of feeling, thinking, and doing is their personality. Personality encompasses thoughts, feelings, and behaviors; interactions with other individuals provide a clearer picture of a person's personality. It consists of the innate and acquired behavioural characteristics that distinguish two people from one another and are observable in their interactions with their environment and social networks. A person's personality [1] is defined by their blend of motivation, behaviour, emotion, and cognitive habits. In a variety of contexts, including e-learning, information filtering, collaboration, and e-commerce, personality recognition models are valuable through user interfaces that adapt to the participation of individual personalities. Personality identification has a wide range of uses, including social network analysis, recommendation engines, fraud detection, sentiment analysis and opinion mining, job satisfaction prediction, success in both romantic and professional relationships, and many more.

Text is categorized using machine learning algorithms based on the sentiment polarity of the text. These machine learning-based approaches approach sentiment classification as a problem akin to document or subject classification. Nevertheless, this method has drawbacks including hard feature extraction, dimensionality expansion, and sparse feature vectors. The terms Big Five and Five-Factor Model [2] are interchangeable. This model, based on real-life observations, gives researchers a common way to talk about and understand the traits that influence how people behave. Psychologists and personality researchers find it useful for

comprehending and analysing personalities. Although there are several ideas on personality, numerous scholars' work on personality theories has led to the development of the Five Factor Model.

Figure 1: OCEAN Personality Prediction Traits

Progress in collecting and accessing data has led to advancements in analytic methods for modelling complex datasets. Many new algorithms now leverage existing data to predict outcomes for unseen data, uncover patterns, or identify similar groups. This process, known as machine learning (ML), encompasses various specialized areas such as it covers a range of specialties including predictive modelling. Supervised learning, statistical learning, recommender systems, unsupervised learning, predictive modeling, and morespanning from the prediction of acute renal damage [5] to computer vision [3] and natural language processing [4].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding and predicting the behaviour of others has been a crucial aspect of human interaction since the earliest days of social interaction among humans. It is probable that our ancestors engaged in various forms of personality assessment long before any written records of such practices existed. In this section, a comprehensive overview is provided of a survey conducted on a personality classification and related methodologies. This aims to pinpoint research gaps and propose solutions for personality classification. As depicted in Figure 8, the review focuses on personality-based sentiment classification, encompassing various deep learning and machine learning methods.

Mawalim et al. [6] an i-vector representing videos of each person speaking, were used to predict their personality attributes. Three separate elements: action, language, and sound—were combined and extracted in various configurations to derive the Big Five personality traits. Pre-trained models were used to compare the model's performance. Such as Ridge Regression (RR), Random Forest (RF), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) with the RF classifier exhibiting encouraging outcomes. Notably, Prediction accuracy was greatly increased by integrating the i-vector characteristics that were retrieved from the audio data. While the approach excelled in predicting some aspects of personality, such high degrees of extraversion and neuroticism, its effectiveness varied. To enhance predictive performance, two different datasets in different languages were employed. Additionally, considering the fusion of multiple models, particularly incorporating motion-related features, showed potential for improving conscientiousness prediction.

In order to identify depression using both verbal and facial clues, Uddin et al. [7] developed a deep learning architecture that included many modalities. The movement of the face is recorded by coding the structural aspects of local dynamic characteristics within the description based on a local structural model. In order to show changes in characteristics at the level of videos and audio segments, they applied the Temporal Pool Method (TAP). The multimodal factorized bilinear pooling (MFB) approach was used by the author to alleviate over-fitting. Video and audio data were divided into predetermined pieces in order to identify spatial attributes and temporal dynamics, To predict the depression score, these characteristics are first pooled using a temporal attentive pooling technique. Multimodal factorized bilinear pooling is then used to combine these modalities, and finally, fully connected and regression layers are applied. The methodologies proposed in this study hold promise for evaluating personality prediction tasks as well.

Using multimodal behavioral information, Salam et al. [8] developed An intricate framework for the Big Five forecasts. After cutting the input video to one minute, participants are divided into two groups according to their gender and Age (Woman ≤ 30 or Man > 30) Then Word embedding and mood elements were extracted from the text, mel-frequency cepstral coefficient attributes (MFCC) from audio, and face and body landmark statistical characteristics were taken from a video. To predict overall personality, decision fusion is utilized, while Neural Architecture Search (NAS) is taught to forecast someone's personality based on individual characteristics. The connections between the various modalities were not taken into account by the fusion. The NAS's ability to enhance search results through morphism—the insertion of a new layer—makes it effective..The effective neural architecture search was made possible by network morphism, and the two top scores were then combined using mean aggregation in Decision Fusion (Late Fusion).

A bilateral recurrent neural network-based sequential model was developed by Lima et al. [9] for automated personality prediction using textual and visual modalities. In contrast to NAS and transformer-based design, this method preserved important using empirical data, personality was predicted. A series of data is created for every participant and supplied to a Multi BiGRU (Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit), which is a sequential model consisting of two gated units. Two gated units in a sequential model, one with a forward classification process and the other with a backward one, after which determines the optimal hyper parameter by averaging all predictions and sending them to auto Keras. But the method was only effective in terms of personality, qualities related to extraversion.

Agrawal et al. [10] merged a person's postures and facial crops, personality prediction utilizing voice, habitat, and an architecture leveraging transformer-based neural network mechanisms. For personality categorization, thirteen distinct facets of an individual's behavior are maintained, and this is coupled with position encoding using LSTM. Concatenating picture feature produce Spatial temporal encodings (STE) ,VGGish audio and user information elements are paired with visual characteristics to generate key-value query pairs that are passed to the transformer-encoder as input. The LSTM receives the transformer's output continuously, combines it with the text, and then forwards it to a layer that is entirely linked for regression. The method is laborious and hasn't been tried on large, common datasets.

Escalante et al. [11] estimated a person's characteristics from interview tapes using deep learning techniques. The initial investigation of explainability in video-based first impressions analysis. To identify personality based on an explainable model's physical characteristics, a employment competition for screening candidates is used as input. The VGG deep learning model is used to obtain the audio and visual

information. Kernel Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) is utilized for feature level fusion, and a random forest classifier is trained on the fused ELM features to categorize the big five personality traits. A 75% accuracy rate was achieved. Cross-modality connections, which may have improved accuracy, are not taken into consideration by feature fusion. In deep learning, the explainable model is viewed as a "black box" model that necessitates an additional mechanism, raising the training cost consequently, and the best solution could be the black box with an open decision-making mechanism.

Lee et al. [12] created a multimodal personality identification system to categorize investor personality attributes for financial advising applications by utilizing text, audio, and video data CNN and LSTM classifiers were used to extract facial landmark features from videos, CNN was utilized to extract speech's time domain signal properties, and Before being categorized into the five main personality traits, 200-dimensional word embedding features that were taken from the text using BiLSTM were fused at the feature level. The authors did not use cross-reference learning from multimodal data to increase accuracy, despite the fact that early and late fusion were examined in this work.

Fodor et al. [13] investigated many transformer designs for assessing personality. The investigation showed that tasks involving personality assessments are better suited for linear frameworks. Three SSL (Self Supervised Learning) models were employed in this experiment: Using Wav2Vec to extract acoustic information from voice input waveforms, FAb-Net for the extraction of visual features, and RoBERTa for text embedding. There is no need for fine-tuning because the model retains its weights. After evaluating quadratic and linear multimodal architecture the author concluded that Lin-MuT, the linear version, performed best under all conditions. It was efficient in terms of memory and computation.

Gao et al. [14] created a multimodal personality categorization system that is cognitively motivated using the concepts of cognitive psychology. The written descriptions of provided by the user after examining the picture is utilized as input. To deduce different qualities of the personality such as hilarious, gloomy, romantic, and so on. BERT extracts text features, while Resnet classifies images. To enhance the CMPC assignment, the model employs two agents: an opinion word selector and an image region selector. Reinforcement learning is used to classify personalities by combining opinion phrases with certain visual regions. LSTM and GRU model the reinforcement learning action sequences known as the Agent-sharing module, followed by a softmax decoder to perform reward sharing, which helps the opinion word and image selector, and lastly, personality classification. This method needs a large volume of dataset and the method is specific to demography. Also not a Big Five model.

The dyadic interaction was taken into consideration by Shao et al. [15], who used the user's facial expressions and the speaker's audio-visual nonverbal cues to determine the listener's personality. Finding a person-specific multimodal that triggers the listener's facial expressions to react to the speaker's audio-visual information is the first step in the process. To determine the listener's personality, the listener's intelligence should then be represented as a graph and fed into a neural network graph. Finding a person-specific multimodal that triggers the listener's facial expressions to react to the speaker's audio-visual information is the first step in the process. The method is time-consuming and does not adhere to the Big Five concept. Moreover, the proposed model has to be taught individually for each person and is not universal.

Giritlioglu et al. [16] classified a personality from images, speech, and text using deep learning methods. Using deep learning techniques, a personality was identified from speech, text, and pictures. The Resnet classifier is used for face pictures, and the CNN-GRU and Regressor use these characteristics to determine the score. Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNN) and Long- and Short-Term Series Networks (LSTNet) were utilized to represent the gaze and head position information. Use Open Pose for body postures, LSTNet for audio, and BERT for transcription Later, there are three stages of fusion: early, late, and hybrid. In contrast to recorded behaviour, the author discovered that induced behaviour infers personality, people express themselves more effectively in society, and the visual modality is more reliable and effective for personality prediction.

Yan et al. [17] examined methods for eliminating bias in multimodality personality recognition systems based on deep learning. The two neutralizing strategies that are being studied are data balancing and adversarial learning. Learning bias was successfully eliminated using both strategies. While adversarial learning increased model precision, data balancing improved performance. First, the author looked at how multimodal fusion is affected by fairness. To evaluate biases in model outcomes, two distinct group fairness measures are developed: Equal Accuracy (EA) and Static Parity (SP). The following biases were identified by our research: (i) Individual behavioral variations amplify biases. (ii) Biases arise from models that have been trained before and incorporate features from several modalities. (iii) As the precision of the model increases, late fusion likewise increases bias. Better outcomes might be obtained by applying our debiasing techniques to multimodal systems in the real world. Learning is centered on the particular modality and is not cross-referenced.

Lin et al. [18] used multimodal traits from audio and video to predict an individual's emotional expressiveness. Quality of Language behavioral data is combined with facial action units

to forecast the expression of emotions. Three questions were investigated in the paper. Features of Facial action units and language behavioral data are integrated to predict emotional expression. The article looked at three questions. To forecast emotional expression, linguistic behavioral data and facial action unit features are combined. Three questions were examined in the paper. Does there consistently exist an association between behavioral indicators of emotional expressiveness? To address these issues, the author developed a predictive model that uses human assessments and extremely accurate transcripts from a video collection for training, validation, and testing. Three techniques were used in the prediction experiments: multilayer perceptrons, support vector regression, and elastic net. Prediction accuracy was increased by combining verbal and behavioral cues, however the approach was only evaluated on small datasets. Lastly, the accuracy of estimating emotional expressiveness is enhanced by factors like the intensity of the facial movement units, the overall word count, and words related to social activities.

Li et al. [19] created a categorization regression net (CR net) that uses text, audio, and text to categorize personalities. The Resnet-34 deep learning model for personality prediction from individual streams was created using the Bell loss function, and The Big Five Personality Traits were predicted by doing regression on the individual data. The procedure begins with categorization; The final accurate prediction is obtained by regressing these attributes using an Extra Trees regressor. We also introduce the Bell Loss function to deal with regression to the mean erroneous predictions. Chalearn's First Impression dataset is used in this study. The learning bias in individual streams and cross-correlation were not taken into consideration by the feature integration.

This tendency was identified through research in machine learning and deep learning perspectives. Figures 2 and 3 indicate that machine learning has accounted for the majority of the effort, using K-Nearest Neighbors (13%), Random Forest (13%), Decision Tree Classifier (20%), Naïve Bayes (20%), and SVM (27%). Additionally, RNN (29%), LSTM (14%), Convolutional Neural Network (15%), GRU(14%), Glov(14%), and AttRCNN(14%), all demonstrated deep learning (Figure7).

Figure2: The Percentage of Machine Learning Algorithm Used for Personality Classification

Figure3: The Percentage of Deep Learning Algorithm Used for Personality Classification

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 4: Proposed Architecture of Personality Classification

1. Machine Learning Algorithms

Logistic Regression: A supervised machine learning technique called logistic regression is efficient when the target class or

dependent variable is binary. Logistic regression is a binary classification approach, so you would have to train distinct models for each of the five personality characteristics. Each feature will have a binary result (e.g., high or low score) depending on an established threshold.

Support Vector Machine: is used for issues involving both regression and classification. Both linear and non-linear jobs may be handled by it. It separates instances into classes while maximizing the margins between them by locating hyper planes across a feature set.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM): is an extremely effective type of recurrent neural network (RNN) for text categorization. The fading gradient and other problems are intended to be addressed by it. A sequence of memory blocks connected by gates, an input layer, many hidden layers, and an output layer comprise the LSTM architecture. An input gate, forget gate, output gate, and cell make up a standard LSTM unit. The pertinent data is gathered when input passes through every tier, while the extraneous information is removed in each cell. As a result, LSTMs do well at remembering certain patterns from data. The classification results are returned by the last fully linked layer, which uses an appropriate activation function.

Convolutional Neural Network: Comprises of three layers: pooling, fully linked layers and convolution. A convolutional layer uses filters to determine the input's feature representation. And find similarities between the features of prior layers. The following one is the pooling layer, which minimizes the spatial size of each matrix inside the feature map, causing the network to perform fewer parameters and calculations. The third layer is the completely linked layer, that conducts high-level reasoning by establishing connections between neurons in the current layer and those in the preceding layer.

Feature Extraction: Machine learning techniques produce an output by learning from a predefined set of features in the training set. Raw text data is turned into a vector of features using feature extraction techniques. Conventional machine learning methods (SVM, LR, etc.) were trained using the features listed below:

Term Frequency (TF): is a mathematical equation that determines how often a word is found in a document throughout a collection. It influences the significance of the word.

Term Frequency-inverse Document Frequency (TFIDF): is a metric that takes into account the number of times the words are found in a document as well as the inverse frequency of these terms across the database. It helps to get past the disadvantages of the BOW strategy.

Pre-trained embedded words are a type of transfer learning in which embeddings learnt from one task are used to another similar task. Embedding in PLMs is learned on large datasets that record both the semantic and syntactic meaning of words. Thus, in the research, pre-trained BERT and GloVe embedding were employed rather than learning word embedding from scratch.

BERT: is a transformer-based machine learning method that models language via an attention mechanism. Static distribution representations for words can be generated by conventional embedding techniques; however they cannot model polysemous words or provide coverage for words that are not in the lexicon. In contrast, BERT offers the advantages of word position consideration, context-dependent embedding, and support for terms that are not in the lexicon. The "BERT-base-uncased" version, which has a 768-dimensional word embedding and a 30,000-word vocabulary, was used in the research.

GloVe: is an international log-bilinear regression model that generates vector visualizations of words. It can surpass tasks like word analogies and similarities or named entity recognition using information from the whole text corpus, a word co-occurrence matrix or term context may be produced.

Dataset: To evaluate the performance of this approach, the My Personality [61] dataset was used, which includes 9,917 status modifications and 250 distinct users on Facebook. These changes in status are classified into categories based on the Big Five distinct personalities paradigm, as seen in Table 1. The My Personality dataset consists of two key items:

Status: The text of a user's post or status update is shown in this column. Our analysis and prediction tasks employ this data as textual input.

Trait Columns: There are five extra columns that correlate to the Big Five personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extroversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. Each row in these trait columns has a binary value (yes or no) that indicates whether a certain personality characteristic is included in the accompanying update on status. The prediction models' desired variables are represented by these trait categories.

Table 1: My Personality Dataset

Value	EXT	NEU	AGR	CON	OPN
Yes	4,210	3,717	5,268	4,556	7,370
No	5,707	6,200	4,649	5,361	2,547

2. Evaluation Matrices

The following multilevel classification criteria were used in this study to detect and categorize different personality characteristics.

- **Accuracy:** measures how many correctly classification labels there are out of all the qualities.
- **Precision:** calculates the average of all instances' percentage of successfully classification labels to total anticipated labels.
- **Recall:** is calculated by dividing the number of successfully classified labels by the mean of all predicted labels.
- **F1-Score:** stands for the precision and recall harmonic mean.

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

We experimented with different techniques. First, we have used Logistic Regression and Support vector machine with TFIDF and TF feature extraction techniques and classify the result. Second we have used CNN and LSTM with BERT and GloVe word embedding algorithms and generate the result. Finally, we have ensemble some of the machine learning algorithms with word embedding and feature extraction techniques and generate prediction probability value and then that value finally classified with the deep neural network as a final classifier.

A DNN-based meta-model and five base-level models (BERT + CNN, BERT + LSTM, GloVe + BiGRU, combined features + SVM, and combined features + LR) comprise the suggested stacked ensemble. The base-level models are first

Table 2: Result of SVM (TFIDF + Features)

Label / Matrices	EXT	AGR	CON	OPN	NEU
SVM (TFIDF + Features)					
Accuracy	64.66	60.03	61.99	77.16	68.54
Precision	56.83	62.63	58.96	81.82	52.66
Recall	47.28	75.74	44.49	90.79	38.05
F1-Score	51.62	68.56	50.71	86.07	44.18

Feed the data preprocessing results. CNN and Bi-LSTM base models use the BERT pre-trained word embeddings as input for their embedding layers, while the GloVe pre-trained word embeddings' word vectors are fed into the BiGRU-based base model's embedding layer. Additionally, TFIDF vectorization is used in conjunction with the combined features. As input for the SVM basis model, In contrast, the LR base uses the TF vectorization as input in combination with characteristics. dsaeaSeveral further tests were carried out in order to provide a more thorough assessment of the success of this strategy. To begin analyzing each model's contribution, Table and Figure display each algorithm's capabilities in relation to each personal feature.

Figure 5: Result of SVM (TFIDF + Features)

Table 3: Result of LR (TF + Features)

Label / Matrices	EXT	AGR	CON	OPN	NEU
LR (TF + Features)					
Accuracy	63.15	59.22	60.98	76.56	68.49
Precision	54.67	62.16	57.63	81.18	52.52
Recall	44.37	74.51	42.43	90.92	38.52
F1-Score	48.98	67.78	48.87	85.77	44.44

Figure 6: Result of LR (TF + Features)

Table 4: Result of LR (CNN + BERT)

Label/ Matrices	EXT	AGR	CON	OPN	NEU
CNN + BERT					
Accuracy	65.99	64.48	62.97	77.07	66.75
Precision	46.92	86.36	50.26	92.38	39.07
Recall	67.74	60.00	64.86	79.46	59.60
F1-Score	55.44	70.80	56.63	85.44	47.20

Figure 7: Result of LR (CNN+BERT)

Figure 9: Result of Proposed Model

Table 5: Result of LSTM + BERT

Label/ Matrices	EXT	AGR	CON	OPN	NEU
LSTM + BERT					
Accuracy	62.75	59.57	62.80	75.50	63.35
Precision	60.75	61.81	61.92	79.83	50.13
Recall	37.74	63.10	53.81	90.47	51.30
F1-Score	46.56	62.45	57.58	84.82	50.71

Evaluating each algorithm's categorization performance separately and the suggested ensemble model in relation to every single personality characteristic, The suggested model obtained the greatest scores for every characteristic, according to the accuracy and F1-score values.

IV. CONCLUSION

A stacked collection framework-based personality detection model that effectively recognizes personality features in social media communications was proposed by this study. A stacked collection framework-based personality detection model that effectively recognizes personality features in social media communications was proposed by this study. Subsequently, pre-processed information is used to train four distinct SVM, LR, CNN, and LSTM are base-level classifiers, and finally, the results of the five basic classifiers are combined into one set of data including the probability of prediction values, The suggested model obtained the greatest scores for every characteristic, according to the accuracy and F1-score values. Experimental findings using My Personality datasets demonstrated that the suggested technique outperforms individual machine learning techniques for personality detection. Furthermore, the suggested ensemble together with other frameworks beat stacking ensemble models and a number of voting, as well as other frameworks highlighted in published studies. The findings indicate that combining standard machine learning techniques based on deep learning produces enhanced outcomes rather to relying just on one of these kinds of algorithms.

Figure 8: Result of LSTM + BERT

Table 6: Result of Proposed Model

Label / Matrices	EXT	AGR	CON	OPN	NEU
Proposed Model					
Accuracy	9.77	69.26	70.52	81.36	72.54
Precision	50.27	89.39	60.73	95.50	43.04
Recall	74.38	63.66	73.41	81.89	73.86
F1-Score	60.01	74.36	66.47	88.17	54.39

The work reported in this research will be expanded to include other emotional concepts in the future. and subjective words such as views, sentiment, emotion, and mood in order to

develop a flexible model for usage in the social network domain.

Further enhancements to this model may include using a bigger collection of balanced personality types for both testing and training, that would result in improved performance of the model. Moreover, two widely used models for predicting personality, the Big-Five models and the MBTI possibly merged to provide a more generalized method for predicting personality types.

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